

Multi-Level Analog Computing-In-Memory FeFET-based Unit Cell for Deep Learning

Ó. Pereira-Rial¹, Hannes Dahlberg², D. García-Lesta¹, V.M. Brea¹, P. López¹, D. Cabello¹, and Lars-Erik Wernersson²

¹*Centro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes (CITIUS), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela*
Santiago de Compostela, Spain. Email: oscar.pereira@usc.es

²*Electromagnetics and Nanoelectronics, Department of Electrical and Information Technology, Lund University*
Lund, Sweden. Email: hannes.dahlberg@eit.lth.se

Abstract—This paper shows a FeFET-based analog multi-level unit cell for computing-in-memory applications for Deep Neural Networks (DNN). The FeFET-based unit cell performs input-weight multiplication with a Back-End-Of-Line (BEOL) ferroelectric HZO FeFET device on top of standard 180 nm CMOS circuits. The unit cell works with a feedback mechanism which combines an in-house FeFET device to store weights and CMOS transistors underneath to provide outputs in current mode to be integrated over time on a capacitor. Said feedback mechanism compensates for device-to-device variability, and would permit to calibrate a system against time variations, something not usually included in cross-bar solutions. Joint electrical simulations of the FeFET-CMOS circuit are performed with a compact Verilog-A model extracted from the experimental characterization of the FeFET devices. Electrical simulations show that our feedback approach leads to a multi-bit cell with 5-bits of resolution, superior to that of state-of-the-art solutions.

Index Terms—FeFET, BEOL, CIM macro, Deep Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep Neural Networks (DNN) feature so many memory accesses on their signal path that today DNN hardware accelerators adopt in-memory computing architectures instead of the classical Von-Neumann approach to reach higher performances. The combination of CMOS and Non-Volatile Memory (NVM) technologies goes one step further as multiply and accumulate operations can be done with said devices, able to store weights for a long time even without power supply.

Ferroelectric FETs (FeFETs) are promising components both for memory and in-memory-computing, owing to their non-volatility, low-power and fast operations [1], [2]. Additionally, the commonly used ferroelectric (FE) $\text{Hf}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ (HZO) shows excellent compatibility with standard CMOS processes [3]. By integrating FE HZO in the gate-stack, the polarization affects the MOSFET channel depletion/accumulation and introduces a threshold voltage (V_T)

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shift. By applying an appropriate read voltage to the gate, the state can be read as either *ON* or *OFF*. A different degree of polarization would shift the V_T accordingly, making multiple states and thus multi-bit operations possible [2].

FeFETs can be realized in scaled Front-End-Of-Line (FEOL). However, challenges arise in this FeFET configuration. Current percolation, limited switching endurance and non-analog states are examples of issues for scaled FEOL FeFETs [4]–[7]. Another alternative is to integrate the FE HZO in the BEOL, connecting a ferroelectric capacitor (FeCAP) in series to the already-existing gate metal. This introduces a controllable polarization that affects the gate but physically separate from the channel, providing a solution to limitations in endurance and percolation [8], [9].

This paper addresses the design of a unit cell for DNN that performs the input-weight multiplication by combining an in-house HZO-based BEOL FeFET device with a standard 180 nm CMOS technology. Our simulations show a multi-bit cell with 5-bits of resolution, which is beyond state-of-the-art solutions [10], [11]. A wafer has been sent for fabrication. Experimental verification of this CIM macro is planned on an upcoming complete system layout and will undergo further studies.

II. FEFET DEVICE CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING

HZO-based FeFET devices were made by integrating FE HZO in the BEOL of a commercial 180 nm CMOS node, provided by XFAB. The CMOS was processed in-house on the top metal 6 layer, where a FeCAP (30 nm TiN, 10 nm HZO, 30 nm TiN) was deposited and connected in series with the CMOS gate. Following, the devices were annealed at 500 °C for 30 s to achieve ferroelectric crystallinity of HZO. The FeCAP area was designed to give a FeCAP-MOS area ratio of 1/9, given a MOS area of 18 μm^2 . A schematic as well as a SEM image of the device integration is illustrated in Fig. 1 (a) and (b), respectively. Electrical measurements were performed using a Keysight B1500 Semiconductor Parameter Analyzer, B1530a Waveform Generators for pulsed measurements and SMUs together with E5288A AttoSense units for I-V measurements.

Fig. 2 shows the I-V transfer characteristics of the FeFET. V_G is the voltage applied to the top electrode of the FeFET

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the FeFET integration by connecting a FE HZO capacitor in series with FEOL CMOS. (b) Falsely colored SEM micrograph illustrating the BEOL processing and FeCAP size determination.

Fig. 2. Experimental I-V transfer characteristics of the FeFET. V_G (V_{WRITE}) is swept with increasing maximum amplitudes ($V_{DS} = 50$ mV) in sequential order. Inset shows the I_D shift as a function of V_{WRITE} (at different $V_G = V_{READ} = 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.25, 1.5$ V, noted in main figure as dashed lines).

(Fig. 1 (a-b)) and can act as both *READ* and *WRITE* voltage. Increasing V_G (as V_{WRITE}) incrementally yields a decrease in V_T , thus enabling a written memory state as either a current at some voltage or a voltage shift defined at some current level. Here, the FeFET drain current (I_D) shift at a certain V_{READ} is modeled. The I_D shift is seen in the Fig. 2 inset for multiple V_{READ} , illustrating the read dependence on the dynamics of the memory state update.

III. ANALOG MULTI-LEVEL CIM UNIT CELL

The design of our analog multi-level CIM unit cell in the CAD tool is performed through a compact Verilog-A model of 16 parameters of the FeFET device seamlessly integrated with CMOS transistors. Said model has been extracted from the experimental I-V in-house FeFET data from Fig. 2.

Our CIM unit cell is a differential current-based cell, meaning that the result of the multiplication is encoded as a proportional current. This output current is then accumulated in a capacitor. By connecting the outputs of multiple unit cells in parallel, forming a column, the dot product of a convolutional neural network (CNN), i.e., a 3D filter, is provided as a voltage on a capacitor. This voltage will be the result of integrating the currents from different cells along time. In our implementation, a BEOL FeFET memory stores the weights,

Fig. 3. Analog multilevel CIM unit cell using the FeFET memory.

W , while CMOS transistors turn the stored weights into output currents depending on the sign and the input data values, which are then converted to voltages on a capacitor. The inputs are coded as PWM signals. The outcome is a highly linear current-time multiplication. Also, the fact that the unit cell features a differential mode preserves weight proportionality, leading to higher accuracy levels [12].

Fig. 3 shows the circuit schematic of the analog multiplier. The FeFET memory provides two biasing voltages, V_P and V_N , for the PMOS and NMOS devices, respectively. These voltages applied to gates of M_P and M_N set the desired output current value when the multiplier is operating. The 1 bit SRAM memory is used to store the sign bit of the weight. If $SIGN = 0$, V_P is connected to the gate of M_P and the gate of M_N is connected to ground, obtaining a positive output current. On the other hand, if $SIGN = 1$, the gate of M_P is connected to the supply voltage and V_N is connected to the gate of M_N , thus providing a negative output current. Switches M_{SP} and M_{SN} are used to activate or deactivate the multiplier through the PWM signal T_{READ} .

The multiplication operation follows this temporal scheme: first, a current proportional to the absolute value of the weight, W , and the sign bit, $SIGN$, is written into the FeFET and SRAM memories, respectively (see Fig. 3). Also, the precharge voltage V_{PCH} is stored on the capacitor C_{sum} . Once the weight values and the initial capacitor value have been set, the M_{SP} and M_{SN} switches are activated for a time T_{READ} proportional to the input, x . Consequently, at the end of the operation, the voltage on the capacitor takes the value given by Eq. (1).

$$V_{C_{sum}} = V_{PCH} + \frac{(-1)^{SIGN}}{C_{sum}} \cdot I(W) \cdot T_{READ}(x) \quad (1)$$

The outcome of a column of unit cells represents a dot product, i.e., a 3D filter of a CNN, and it is the voltage $V_{C_{sum}}$ on the per-column capacitor C_{sum} .

The FeFET based analog memory can be seen in Fig. 4. The core of the memory consists of the ferroelectric capacitor

Fig. 4. FeFET memory to store the weights W of the unit cell.

Fig. 5. Structural diagram of the FeFET writing mechanism.

FeCAP and the NMOS transistor M_{FeFET} , both forming the FeFET device. The diode connected transistors M_{DP} and M_{DN} determine the biasing voltages V_P and V_N to be used in the analog multiplier. The rest of transistors are the switches that determine the different operating modes of the memory. These modes are *Reset*, *Write* and *Read*. In mode *Reset*, the drain and source of M_{FeFET} are connected to the supply voltage while the FeCAP voltage is connected to ground. With this configuration, the voltage across the FeFET is negative and therefore the device will be erased. In *Write* mode, both drain and source of M_{FeFET} are connected to ground and the FeCAP is connected to a V_{WRITE} voltage. The greater V_{WRITE} , the larger will be the channel current of the device M_{FeFET} . Finally, in *Read* mode, M_{FeFET} is connected to the diode connected transistors M_{DP} and M_{DN} , and the FeCAP is connected to a sufficiently low V_{READ} voltage to avoid altering the state of the FeFET device.

In the *Read* mode, the M_{FeFET} current flows through M_{DP} and M_{DN} thus providing the biasing voltages V_P and V_N . It is worth noting that the memory energy consumption is nearly zero when it is neither being read nor written, which significantly reduces the static standby power consumption of a circuit incorporating a substantial amount of these memories.

The writing mechanism of weights W into the FeFET

Fig. 6. Circuit to generate V_{WRITE} voltages for the FeFET memory writing.

memory is shown in Fig. 5. After the *Reset* action, the writing process begins with a feedback mechanism. In this mechanism, the desired value, V_{ref} , is compared to the voltage V_N , which is obtained from writing each positive single-slope voltage V_{WRITE} in the FeFET memory and read the stored current. The writing process is finished when V_N overcomes V_{ref} . The circuit of Fig. 5 would be shared by the unit cells of a column to perform the dot product of a CNN. It should be noted that this feedback system of Fig. 5 permits to improve the accuracy of a multi-cell level during inference, accounting for static and dynamic non-idealities of the FeFET memory.

The digital controller provides the different signals to control the FeFET memory as well as the V_{WRITE} generator block. The reference voltage V_{ref} is determined by the diode-connected M_{ref} through which the target current I_{ref} is flowing.

The V_{WRITE} signal is generated with the switched-capacitor circuit with the two non-overlapping signals Φ_1 and Φ_2 displayed in Fig. 6. The output voltage V_{WRITE} follows the expression:

$$V_{WRITE}(N) = V_L \left(\frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha} \right)^N + \frac{1}{\alpha} V_H \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\alpha^i}{(1 + \alpha)^i} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of cycles from reset, being every cycle a sequence of signals Φ_1 and Φ_2 in HIGH, V_L is the low voltage for V_{WRITE} , V_H is the high voltage and $\alpha = C_2/C_1$ is the capacitance ratio.

The aim of this switched-capacitor circuit is to provide a finer resolution or control on the FeFET output current, which, in turn, allows for more resolution of our multi-bit CIM cell. The overall effect on the FeFET output current can be seen in Fig. 7, where V_{WRITE} and the output current of the FeFET are plotted against time, expressed in number of cycles N . The V_{WRITE} variation according to Eq. (2) leads to a more lineal behavior along time in the output current of the FeFET, which, in turn, permits to enlarge the distance among states, and with that, the resolution of our unit CIM cell. It should be noted the simplicity of our switched-capacitor approach when compared to more complex solutions like those based on digital circuits and digital to analog converters to perform the same function.

The writing process of the memory can be seen in the simulated response shown in Fig. 8. As observed, consecutive writes and reads on the FeFET-based memory increment the value of V_N until it reaches the value V_{ref} . At this point, the comparator output, CMP , switches to HIGH, indicating the end of the process, as signaled by the $DONE$ output

Fig. 7. Simulated output voltage of the V_{WRITE} generator circuit and corresponding output current of the FeFET device.

Fig. 8. Transistor level simulation of the FeFET analog memory writing process.

of the digital controller. It is important to highlight that the comparator features power gating, which helps reduce the average power consumption of the system. This is the reason for the RC-type decay observed in the CMP voltage at the end of the process shown in the top of Fig. 8.

The output of our current-based CIM unit cell is shown in Fig. 9. This figure collects the output current for positive and

Fig. 9. Simulated output current of the multiplier in Fig. 3 for different target currents I_{ref} .

Fig. 10. Layout of the CMOS part of the analog multiplier designed with FeFET memories. The FeCAP integration is planned for post-fabrication processing between contacts VIA 1 and VIA 2.

negative values, i.e., signal $SIGN$ of the circuit shown in Fig. 3 set to 0 and 1, respectively. These simulations are the result of the combination of the circuits displayed in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, and Fig. 5. These simulations correspond to a 5-bit multiplication, where the least significant bit has been set to 40 nA.

Fig. 10 illustrates the layout of the CMOS components in the proposed analog multiplier using FeFET memories. The FeCAP device is built between VIA 1 and VIA 2 during post-fabrication processing. The total silicon area occupied by the layout is approximately $462 \mu\text{m}^2$. To give a general context, this area is significantly smaller than that of the only CMOS multiplier circuit designed with the same structure of current-time multiplication reported in [13], which occupies approximately $970 \mu\text{m}^2$. Finally, it should be noted that in comparison with other solutions like that of reference [10], which features 2-bits of resolution, our approach works with 5-bits in simulation thanks to the CMOS feedback mechanism to write the FeFET memory, which makes our design more robust to device-to-device and time variations when compared to cross-bar solutions.

IV. OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a FeFET-based analog multi-level unit cell designed for computing-in-memory applications in Deep Neural Networks. Our design incorporates a feedback mechanism that combines FeFET devices for weight storage with CMOS transistors to provide current-mode outputs, which are integrated over time on a capacitor. This feedback mechanism compensates the device-to-device variability as well as the possible variation due to the device aging.

Electrical simulations using a compact Verilog-A model derived from experimental characterizations of our in-house FeFET devices demonstrates that our feedback approach achieves at least 5-bit resolution, extending the range of 2-bits of the current state-of-the-art experimental results in multi-bit FeFET cells. Further experimental results of our approach will show if this statement still holds.

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